

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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Harmful Algal Blooms in a Changing Climate

In September 2019 the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) approved and accepted the *Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* (SROCC) at its 51st Session [1]. This report was notable for many reasons, but of particular note was that an IPCC report identified “increased frequency in coastal areas since the 1980s of harmful algal blooms, attributed to both climatic and non-climatic drivers, with *high confidence*”, meaning that experts agreed that there was medium to high agreement and robust evidence for this statement. In contrast the last major IPCC report published in 2014 (AR5 Chapters 5-6), just 5 years ago, reported limited evidence and low confidence for future climate change effects on HABs. In the most recent report there was also high confidence that trends in HABs were associated with ocean warming, marine heatwaves, oxygen loss, eutrophication and pollution, and high confidence that these events have had negative impacts on food security, tourism, local economies, and human health. Vulnerability to HAB events was linked to areas without sustained monitoring programs and early warning systems (medium confidence).

For some this statement from the IPCC may seem premature given that linking climate change and HABs has previously been identified as a “formidable predictive challenge” [2], and there are nearly as many questions as answers regarding climate interactions with HAB events [3,4]. Despite these questions the overall scientific consensus has shifted rapidly in the last 5-10 years.

The SROCC report cites several specific examples of climate-induced changes in HAB events, including range expansion of warm-water organisms such as *Gambierdiscus*, contraction of cold-water species, detection of novel phycotoxins and toxic species, and re-

gional increases in frequency and intensity of toxic blooms, such as the *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* event in the eastern Pacific during 2015 and the record HAB events in Chile during 2016 caused by *Pseudochattonella* cf. *verruculosa* and *Alexandrium catenella*. Further evidence was documented from experimental studies linking multiple drivers to enhanced HAB activity, such as the synergistic effects of increasing CO₂ and temperature.

It is important to note that the SROCC report clearly identified the combined effects of both climate change (e.g. rising temperatures, decreasing pH) and global change attributed to human activity (e.g. eutrophication and pollution) as important drivers. SROCC identified the greatest risk for estuarine organisms because HABs are stimulated by riverine nutrient loads and exacerbated by warming and lower dissolved oxygen and pH associated with these environments. This inevitably leads to HAB-related risks for coastal biodiversity and ecosystem services.

SROCC also noted that there is considerable variability in HAB responses at a local and regional scale. It was suggested that regional variations could be explained by spatial differences in climate drivers such as temperature, water column stratification, ocean acidification, precipitation and extreme weather events, as well as by non-climatic drivers such as eutrophication and pollution.

SROCC makes several key points that provide a roadmap for ongoing efforts. First, HAB occurrence, toxicity, and risk are projected to increase with warming and rising CO₂. Second, increasing likelihood of occurrences of HABs under climate change elevates associated risks to fisheries, aquaculture and tourism as well as public health. Third, there is *limited evidence* that re-

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New Initiative on Fish-Killing Algal Blooms

An "Advanced International Colloquium and Technical Workshop on Fish-Killing HABs" under the auspices of IOC-IPHAB and GlobalHAB, and with the support of the government of Chile through CORFO and collaboration of CREAM-IFOP, was held in Puerto Varas, Chile, 8 – 11 October 2019. Ten invited participants (D.M. Anderson, A.D. Cembella (WG chair, apologies), O. Espinoza, L. Guzman, G.M. Hallegraef, P.J. Hansen (acting chair), H. Hegaret, T.O. Larsen, J. Mardones, M. Iwataki, L. MacKenzie) reviewed the state-of-knowledge on fish-killing algal blooms (Fig. 1).

The socio-economic impacts from fish-killing microalgal blooms are much greater on a global scale than those from HAB species causing seafood biotoxin accumulation and contamination. Examples are the 1973 *Chattonella marina* bloom in the Seto Inland Sea, Japan (estimated US\$71M loss to sea bream aquaculture), the 1988 *Prymnesium polylepis* bloom in the European Kattegat with wide-scale marine ecosystem impacts, and the 2015/16 *Pseudochattonella verruculosa* bloom in Chile (US\$800M loss to salmon aquaculture). Highly potent fish-killers include the globally distributed, taxonomically unrelated flagellate groups *Alexandrium*, *Margalefidinium* (*Cochlodinium*), *Chattonella*, *Heterosigma*, *Pseudochattonella/Vicicitus*, *Karenia*, *Karlodinium*, *Prymnesium/Chrysochromulina* which all produce lytic compounds that irreparably damage the sensitive gill tissues of fish

which then die from suffocation. With perhaps a single exception (*Karenia brevis* in Florida), none of these fish-killing algal blooms have ever caused human health problems from seafood consumption, which partially explains the limited attention these HABs previously have attracted. Except for recent advances with *Prymnesium* (*prymnesins*) and *Karlodinium* (*karlotoxins*), the precise mechanisms of how such microalgae kill finfish remain poorly understood. *Pseudochattonella* is particularly poorly understood, with high ichthyotoxicity in nature but limited potency observed in culture studies. While some species are always ichthyotoxic, others such as *Heterosigma* and *Alexandrium catenella* cause problems only under special environmental conditions. Progress in this field has been hindered by the use of widely different bioassay systems (*Artemia*, blood and fish gill RT1 cell lines, embryos, juvenile and adult fish) and lack of analytical chemical methods and reference materials to quantify and characterize so-called "ichthyotoxins". Furthermore these compounds cause problems in extremely low concentrations dissolved in an aqueous medium, as opposed to the well known toxins PST, DST, AST, NST bioaccumulating in high concentrations in seafood. Essentially similar ichthyotoxins also adversely impact shellfish, shellfish hatcheries and aquariums that draw in water from bloom affected areas. Climate change is adding to the unpredictability of such rapid fish killing blooms and puts

further pressure on seafood security for an ever increasing human population. Fish-killing HABs can be compared to disastrous forest fires, and not doing anything is no longer deemed acceptable. Prevention, prediction and monitoring are no longer sufficient, and we actively need to pursue strategies to stop the blooms, for example by means of clay flocculation of algal biomass and/or mopping up of ichthyotoxins.

The working group reviewed our knowledge of algal taxonomy, toxin chemistry, modes of action, fish-killing mechanisms, bioassays, broader ecosystem impacts, role of climate change, and options for prevention, control and mitigation. A well-attended open conference, accessible via webinar, and a visit to a local salmon farm formed part of the workshop. A follow-up session on fish-killing HABs is next scheduled for ICHA 2020 in Mexico, and a dedicated journal issue on this topic is being planned.

Some of the presentations are available on the link below; <https://www.facebook.com/1871967802832922/videos/1254975338037553/>.

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Invited speakers and hosts of the "Advanced International Colloquium and Technical Workshop on Fish-Killing HABs" Puerto Varas, Chile October 8-11, 2019. Photo courtesy of Oscar Espinosa, IFOP.

IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB Workshop: Evaluating, Reducing and Mitigating the Cost of Harmful Algal Blooms: a Compendium of Case Studies

Over the last two decades, several reports have compiled what is known about the economic impacts of harmful algal blooms (HABs) [1-4]. Although these reports attempted to gather comprehensive economic impact data, both the type and amount of data available were limited. One past study estimated the cost of HABs in the European Union at \$800 Million [2] but most of that cost was extrapolated for a very few HAB organisms. Furthermore, most countries have neither conducted economic analyses of HABs nor collected data that can be used to generate reliable quantitative estimates of net economic losses and economic impacts. The lack of data, appropriate and standardized protocols, and the dearth of peer-reviewed studies hampers efforts to quantify the societal costs of increasingly frequent, intense and long-lasting HAB events and to help evaluate the cost of various strategies being developed for HAB pre-

vention, control, and mitigation.

To strategize how specific economic studies can be used to assess the economic impacts of HAB and mitigate their risks, a joint GlobalHAB-PICES workshop was held on 17-19 October, 2019, prior to the annual meeting of the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES). During this 2.5-day workshop, over 48 international experts on economics and the science of HABs from the USA, Japan, Australia, Canada, Korea, the UAE, China, France, Norway, Chile, Scotland, Spain, and the UK discussed a compendium of case studies that highlight the economic impacts of HABs on farmed salmon and shellfish and on wild-caught, reef-based fisheries.

Workshop discussion topics included the net impacts of HABs, their costs, and coastal resilience to HABs worldwide. Plenary lectures included worldwide examples of wild fisheries, recreational fisheries and aquaculture losses.

The five case studies were: 1. US west coast *Pseudo-nitzschia* and impacts on shellfish and marine mammals; 2. Korea *Margalefidinium (=Cochlodinium) polykridoides* including impacts on wild and aquacultured fish kills; 3. Ciguatera fish poisoning; 4. Fish aquaculture including examples from the E.U., Canada, Chile; and 5. Shellfish aquaculture losses.

The economic impact of HABs is recognized to be large, although currently poorly quantified in many of the world's coastal areas. The losses faced by insurers are huge. At the workshop, a representative from a reinsurance company specified that 45% of insurance claims are now from HABs. In fact, it was stated that the loss due to HABs is larger than any storm that insurers have ever faced. In the Republic of Korea, an insurer has already collapsed due to frequent and enormous losses of aquaculture fish due to HABs.

Participants at the GLOBALHAB Workshop: Evaluating, Reducing and Mitigating the Cost of Harmful Algal Blooms, at the Victoria, British Columbia, Convention Center from 17-19 October 2019.

Several examples of HAB-related losses and loss mitigation were discussed at the workshop in detail. A HAB incident in northern Norway alone resulted in the loss of 14 thousand tons of Atlantic salmon in May 2019, resulting in a total loss of at least 330 million USD, including insured losses of 45 million USD, underinsured values and deductibles of 40 million USD, losses of future salmon sales at 160 million USD, cleanup costs at 30-40 million USD, and loss of taxes and unemployment benefits at 50 million USD. In Brittany, France, the Laboratoire d'Économie et de Management de Nantes-Atlantique (LEMNA), University of Nantes, is conducting a detailed estimation of the impacts of shellfish trade bans caused by HABs. Researchers at LEMNA are creating a database documenting these trade bans from 2004 through 2018 at shellfish harvesting areas in four French departments (Finistère, Morbihan, Loire-Atlantique and Vendée). These four areas encompass about 700 shellfish farms representing 37,600 tonnes of products with an estimated value €141 million, i.e. 20% of the national shellfish harvest.

Finally, breakout groups discussed strategies for mitigation including the value of information from better or more refined forecasts. Questions addressed included: Can contingency planning reduce loss? How do we open areas more quickly, how do we make closures shorter, and what is the value of information from better forecasts? What is the cost benefit analysis of mon-

itoring programs? How much should be spent on monitoring? For insurance purposes, how do we reduce the cost of HABs?

The huge HAB-related losses to industry, consumers and governments illustrate the need for insurers, aquaculturists, public health professionals, economists, and HAB scientists to work together to estimate the cost of HAB events relative to the costs of mitigation and management. Studies of economic and social losses and their impacts need to be planned and teams need to be formed prior to HAB events to ensure that they are comprehensively studied. Toward this goal, the workshop further helped to establish greater connections between economists, industry scientists, and HAB researchers. Participants plan to refine and publish case studies to help guide future research and management priorities. A series of white papers are being prepared to document the workshop goals, the five case study examples, and summary recommendations for the future. These white papers will be published on the GlobalHAB and PICES websites. A summary of this work will be published in a peer-reviewed paper, providing several examples that can be used to steer future studies on the economic impact of HABs.

The workshop was co-sponsored by GlobalHAB and PICES with the support of the Scientific Committee on Ocean Research (SCOR), the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA), Northwest Pacific Action Plan Coastal Environmental Assessment Regional

Activity Centre (NOWPAP CEARAC), Greig Seafood Ltd., the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, and AXA XL Reinsurance.

References

1. Anderson DM et al, 2000. WHOI-2000-11 Technical Report, 96 pp
2. Hoagland P et al 2006. In: Granéli E & Turner JT (eds) *Ecology of Harmful Algae. Ecological Studies (Analysis and Synthesis)*, vol 189. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg
3. Huppert DD & Trainer VL 2014. In: Trainer VL & Yoshida T. *Proc WS Economic impacts of harmful algal blooms on fisheries and aquaculture. PICES Sci. Report No 47*, PICES, Sidney, BC Canada, pp 59-71
4. Sanseverino I et al 2006. JRC Technical Report. EUR 27905 EN, doi:10.2788/66047.

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duction of non-climatic anthropogenic stressors can reduce the risk of HABs without also mitigating climate change. Finally, risks will be greatest in poorly monitored areas, and poleward distributional shifts of HAB organisms may exacerbate our ability to monitor HAB organisms and impacts.

Wells et al [3] identified two central goals to improve our understanding of HABs and climate change. First, to obtain compelling evidence that climate change has altered HAB distribution, prevalence, and character. Second, to develop the theoretical, experimental, and empirical evidence for these chang-

es. SROCC argues that there is clear consensus for the former, and that the latter, combined with a renewed emphasis on documenting the efficacy of mitigation strategies, would increase our ability to predict how HABs will respond to climate change and to respond appropriately. As has been stated numerous times in the past we require a renewed commitment to global observation systems through efforts such as the Global Ocean Observing System and GlobalHAB so as to quantitatively monitor the multiple interacting factors shaping our ocean's future [2-5].

References

1. IPCC 2019. SROCC Report <https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/>
2. Hallegraeff GM 2010. *J Phycol* 46(2): 220-235
3. Wells ML et al 2015. *Harmful Algae* 49: 68-93
4. Wells ML et al (in press). *Harmful Algae* p.101632
5. Anderson DM et al 2012. *Annu Rev Mar Sci*: 143-176

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Massive fish mortality in Teluk Bahang, Penang, Malaysia caused by a hypoxia-inducing algal bloom

Fish kill events due to algal blooms have been increased dramatically over the past decades. Several massive fish kill events have been reported in Malaysia [1-5]. Among the incidents reported, some are caused by toxins (ichthyotoxic, hemolytic, cytotoxic) released by harmful microalgae while others are due to high biomass blooms leading to dissolved oxygen depletion (hypoxia and anoxia)[1-5].

On August 11, 2019, a massive fish kill event was reported in Teluk Bahang, Penang, Malaysia (Fig. 1a). The local farmers claimed losses of over 50 tons of caged fish, with an estimated worth of USD 190,000 (Fig. 1b). Abnormal fish behaviors were observed by the fish farmers, as they noticed the caged fish jumped aggressively the night before the fish kill event occurred.

A rapid response field sampling study was conducted in the area (August 13-14, 2019) to investigate the cause of this fish kill event. Water samples were collected from four stations, St1 (near

the river mouth), St2 (fish cage area – 0.5 km away from shoreline), St3 (2.1 km away from shoreline), and St4 (4.3 km away from shoreline) (Fig. 2). Water temperatures ranged from 30.1 – 30.7 °C, salinity from 30.8 – 31.6, while pH was relatively low, in the range of 7.42 – 7.69.

Dissolved oxygen (DO) levels in the water column were depleted; the lowest DO levels were observed at St 2 (fish cage area), with surface values as low as 2.47 mg/L, and 0.94 mg/L at the bottom (4 m depth) (Fig. 2b). These values were much lower than the recommended minimum DO requirement for tropical marine fish, i.e. 5 mg/L (75% saturation). A 24-h monitoring of DO levels revealed that surface (~1 m) values dropped drastically at night from ~8 mg/L to 1.93 mg/L, but rose steadily in the morning. Hypoxia occurs and conditions become unsuitable for any mariculture activity when dissolved oxygen levels fall below 2 mg/L [6].

Macronutrient concentrations at

the study sites were determined spectrophotometrically. The highest nitrate and silicate concentrations, 25 μM and 21 μM , respectively, were observed at St2. The Chl-*a* (53.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$) maximum was also observed at this station. Microscopic phytoplankton analysis showed a high abundance of *Proboscia* sp., *Rhizosolenia* sp., *Chaetoceros* spp., *Guinardia* sp., *Coscinodiscus* spp., and *Leptocylindrus* sp. *Coscinodiscus* sp. was the dominant genus in all stations, with a maximum of 2.5×10^4 cells/L (Fig. 2c). Fish-killing dinoflagellates and raphidophytes were not observed at the samples. Most likely, excessive nutrient levels were one of the drivers inducing massive phytoplankton blooms in this area. The bloom-induced hypoxia reported here had a severe negative impact on the local aquaculture.

References

1. Lim PT et al 2012. *Sains Malaysiana* 41: 509-1515
2. Lim HC et al 2014. *Harmful Algae* 40: 51-62
3. Teng ST et a. 2016. *HAN* 52: 5
4. Anton A et al 2008. *Harmful Algae* 7: 331-336
5. Shah MF Star Online 2019. <https://www.thestar.com.my/news/nation/2019/09/08/dead-fish-incident-johor-fisheries-dept-says-stagnant-water-must-be-treated-first-before-being-released>.
6. Diaz RJ. & DL Breitburg 2009. *Academic Press*. p. 1-23

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Fig. 1. (a) Map of Peninsular Malaysia showing the location of Teluk Bahang, Penang. (b) Fish kill phenomenon in a fish farm at Teluk Bahang (photo credit to [5]).

Fig. 2. (a) Sampling stations. (b) Dissolved oxygen levels (mg/L) in the study site. (c) Light micrograph of *Coscinodiscus* sp., scale bar = 20 μm .

Blooms of the potentially harmful raphidophyte *Chattonella antiqua* and the occurrence of the epiphytic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* in the coastal waters of Alexandria, Egypt

Fig. 1. Location of sampling stations

This article reports blooms of two harmful microalgal species, a raphidophyte and a dinoflagellate, at two localities, El Dekhila and Abou Qir, at the western and eastern sides of Alexandria coastal waters, south Mediterranean (Fig. 1).

Blooms of *Chattonella antiqua* (Y. Hada) C. Ono 1980

Chattonella antiqua is a unicellular, biflagellated raphidophyte frequently found in the plankton of temperate nutrient-rich coastal waters under a wide range of environmental conditions [1-3]. Members of the *Chattonella* genus can form harmful algal blooms (HABs) that cause massive mortalities of wild and cultivated fish via the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS, e.g. superoxide). These ROS are responsible for gill tissue injury and mucus production that kill fish [1-2,4]. *Chattonella antiqua*, was also found to produce brevetoxins [5]. These microalgae are the focus in monitoring studies in some

coastal marine areas. Blooms of this genus are usually accompanied by golden-brown seawater discoloration due to their high content of fucoxanthins [3,6].

The El Dekhila area is part of Mex Bay, western Alexandria. This is a highly eutrophic marine basin due to the huge amounts of domestic sewage, industrial wastewater, and agricultural run-off from different land based sources (estimated as $7-8 \times 10^6$ m³ per day), discharged directly into the sea, or indirectly from Lake Mariout. The area, considered ecologically, economically and socially important, is an extremely variable system. High inputs of nutrients and organic matter of anthropogenic origin may create favourable conditions for the development of recurrent massive harmful algal blooms causing fish and invertebrate mortality [7]. Blooms of *C. antiqua* have been previously described in Alexandria waters [1], and its presence as a member of the local phytoplankton community was reported several decades ago [7].

Cell densities of *C. antiqua* (Fig. 2) in surface waters of the El Dekhila area during the summer of 2019 reached up to 16.7×10^6 cells l⁻¹, causing reddish water discoloration. The bloom appeared associated with high temperatures, intermediate salinity and extremely high nutrient loads (Table 1). The observed physico-chemical conditions are not very different from those observed previously associated with the occurrence of red tides in Alexandria waters. Among the co-occurring phytoplankton species, *Chaetoceros compressus* (4.1×10^6 cell l⁻¹), *Skeletonema costatum* (0.28×10^6 cell l⁻¹), and *Leptocylindrus minimus* (0.16×10^6 cell l⁻¹) thrived during these bloom conditions. This is the second report of massive *C. antiqua* blooms in Alexandria. During the 2006 bloom [1], a few cells of *Heterosigma*, which later became a red tide bloom species in the area, were observed [7].

Due to their tolerance to a wide range of environmental conditions, it may be assumed that blooms of raphidophytes in Alexandria waters are more common than has hitherto been documented in the literature.

Currently the Egyptian government is implementing a substantial initiative to improve the water quality of Lake Mariout. Reduction of nutrient loads would be one of the best strategies to mitigate blooms of the genus *Chattonella* and other potentially harmful algal species in Mex Bay.

Epiphytic *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*

In the last few decades there have been an increasing number of reports worldwide detailing the geographical expansion and impacts of epiphytic microalgal species belonging to the genus *Ostreopsis* in temperate areas [8,9]. *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* is known to produce toxins and its toxicity is associated with the presence of palytoxin analogues [10]. In the Mediterranean Sea, neurotoxic effects due to ingestion of seafood contaminated with *Ostreopsis*-related toxins transferred through the food web have not yet been reported. So far, blooms of certain *Ostreopsis* species are implicated only in mild respiratory, skin and eye irritation [11]. A review of the existing literature over the last three decades on harmful red tide blooms in Alexandria coastal waters has been performed and focuses on planktonic bloom forming species [12]. Information on the ecology of potentially harmful epiphytic dinoflagellates from Alexandria coastal waters is extremely poor. Planktonic stages of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* were recorded in the study area in July 2007, but maximal density reached (1980 cells l⁻¹) was well below the alert values [13].

The relationship between environmental factors and the abundance of epiphytic *O. cf. ovata* cells in Abou Qri was investigated. This is a highly exposed rocky area in eastern Alexandria.

Fig. 2. Micrographs of *Chattonella antiqua* (Y.Hada) C. Ono

Table 1. Seawater physical and chemical parameters during the summer 2019 *Chattonella* bloom

°C	Salinity	pH	mg O ₂ /L		Nutrient concentration µM				
			DO	COD	PO ₄	SiO ₄	NO ₂	NO ₃	NH ₄
35.00	17.8	8.64	6.3	22.5	13.35	58	12.6	20.6	45.2

Table 2. Physical and chemical properties of seawater in the study area

Parameter	°C	Salinity	pH	DO	DO%	NO ₂	NO ₃	NH ₄	TN	SiO ₄	PO ₄
May	25,1	37,2	8,37	10,4	61,5	3	11,02	2,5	16,52	0,12	0,66
July	28,37	35,43	8,59	9,35	39,2	1,2	8,34	2,8	12,34	5,64	5,44
October	22,34	36,6	8,11	2,65	139,2	1,5	10,1	1,2	12,8	0,62	1
February	17,63	35,8	8,65	3,58	163,1	2,34	7,8	2,2	12,34	0,45	0,39
Mean	23,36	36,26	8,43	6,50	100,75	2,01	9,32	2,18	13,50	1,71	1,87
S.D.	4,54	0,80	0,24	3,94	59,71	0,82	1,50	0,69	2,02	2,63	2,39

Table 3. The abundance of *Ostreopsis cf ovata* attached to Chlorophyta, Rhodophyta and Phaeophyta macroalgae.

May	St. I		St. II		July	St. I		St. II	
Macroalgae	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%	Macroalgae	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%
Chlorophyta									
Total	401.06	63.84	325.50	66.50	Total	60.49	9.63	38.10	7.78
Mean	133.69		108.50		Mean	20.16		12.70	
SD	102.06		88.71		SD	24.11		17.07	
Rhodophyta									
Total	227.19	10.15	164.00	9.35	Total	12.77	2.03	8.70	1.78
Mean	75.73		54.67		Mean	6.39		4.35	
SD	64.76		46.28		SD	4.08		3.26	
Phaeophyta									
Total	10.80	0.09	9.35	1.90	Total	1.06	5.65	0.78	2.89
Mean	5.40		3.10		Mean	0.35		0.26	
Standard Dev	0.57		0.49		SD	0.10		0.11	
October	St. I		St. II		February	St. I		St. II	
Macroalgae	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%	Macroalgae	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%	Cell g fw ⁻¹	%
Rhodophyta									
Total	7.4	10.41	1.1	1.55	Total	1.06	5.65	0.78	2.89
Mean	2.47		0.37		Mean	0.35		0.26	
SD	3.67		0.46		SD	0.10		0.11	

Measurements of physical and chemical parameters at the sampling sites are given in Table 2. Salinity values didn't show a particular seasonal variation, and pH values were very stable. Dissolved oxygen levels in May and July were 3.5-3.9 times greater than the minimum in October. Nitrite concentrations exhibited the typical summer minimum, and it was highest in May. Nitrate concentrations were always high, and represented > 60% of the total estimated nitrogenous resources. Ammonia concentrations were often <3 µM, and reached a minimum in October. Silicate values were the lowest in May, with a maximum of 5.6 µM in July. Phosphate trends followed that of silicate.

Abundance on the thalli of 14 differ-

ent macroalgae species was estimated during a full year sampling. Analysis of variance showed significant differences in abundance between seasons and macroalgal hosts. Water temperature and nutrients (NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻ and PO₄³⁻) seemed to be the major factors affecting the abundance of *Ostreopsis cf ovata*. Salinity variations exhibit a weak, insignificant influence on the abundance of specimens attached to Chlorophyta spp., and a negligible effect for those on Rhodophyta spp. (Table 3).

The *Ostreopsis* maximum (Fig. 3) was found in summer (July) associated with the highest water temperature (28.4 °C), while its minimum was recorded in winter (February) at a much lower temperature (17.6 °C). Tempera-

ture is a key factor determining the *Ostreopsis* blooms, but on site-specific bases, its dynamics and distribution in summer is driven by a combination of light intensity, wave activity, etc. Allelopathy has also been suggested among the biotic factors crucial to *Ostreopsis* occurrence [14].

Although *O. cf ovata* was found on all of the examined macroalgae, its abundance was ranked between Chlorophyta > Rhodophyta > Phaeophyta. The highest abundance was observed between spring and autumn with the peak on chlorophycean species in July, followed by a sharp decline in winter with the minimum in February (Table 3). The results showed relevant differences in the abundance of *O. cf ovata* depending on the macroalgal host species. The Chlorophytes *Ulva linza*, followed by *U. fasciata* and *U. compressa* seemed particularly suitable to support relatively high abundances of *Ostreopsis* during May and July; abundance was relatively less on *U. lactuca* in October. Our results suggest Chlorophytes might be an optimal macroalgal substrate for epiphytic *Ostreopsis* in the study area. Conversely, previous studies in the Mediterranean showed that the Ulvaceae constituted the substrate of least preference. Some factors, such as the sampling protocol and seasonality of the macroalgae, may explain these discrepancies. As for the Rhodophyta, the maximum abundance was found on *Corallina (=Ellisolandia) officinalis* in July and October. The occurrence of Phaeophyta species was restricted to May and July, and among them, *Padina pavonia* contained the highest abundances.

In summary, *Ostreopsis cf ovata* may pose an additional threat to public health and the economy of Alexandria. Temperature, PO₄ and NO₃ seemed to be the main factors influencing its abundance. *Ostreopsis cf ovata* had the ability to attach to diverse macroalgae species, with preference for Chlorophyta. Since *O. cf ovata* cells are loosely attached to the substrata and can be easily removed and re-suspended in the water column, future studies about their relation with wave dynamics should be addressed. To our knowledge, this is the first ecological study of epiphytic forms of this species during a full annual cycle in the SE

Continued on page 16

First records of *Gambierdiscus excentricus* and *Ostreopsis lenticularis* in the Cape Verde Archipelago (Macaronesia, Central Eastern Atlantic)

Fig. 1. Map of Cape Verde archipelago (Macaronesia Region).

Harmful algal blooms (HAB) species frequently recorded in tropical latitudes are apparently increasing their distribution in temperate areas [1]. This expansion is linked both to naturally occurring changes, such as global warming, as well as anthropogenic causes such as ship ballast water transport, nutrient loading, marine habitat deterioration and expanding aquaculture [2]. These changes are allowing the establishment of HAB species in areas where they were previously unknown. In some areas, this has been well studied, whereas in others the only evidence of the presence of these species is the harmful impact they have had on marine organisms, the environment and human health.

Macaronesia is a name used to designate several archipelagos of volcanic origin in the Atlantic off the south west coast of Europe and north west of Afri-

ca; the Azores and Madeira (Portugal), the Canary Islands (Spain) and Cape Verde. There are no reports on the occurrence of ciguatoxins (CTXs) and maio toxins (MTXs)-producing dinoflagellates in Cape Verde.

Currently, the only information available on microalgae in the Cape Verde Islands was published by Silva in 1956 from material collected in Boa Vista Island in 1948 [3]. Silva's study included the first report of a presumed *Gambierdiscus* species named as *Goniodoma* sp. Fraga and Rodríguez described a new benthic dinoflagellate species, *Gambierdiscus silvae*, in the Canary Islands and suggested that probably corresponded to Silva's original description of *Goniodoma* sp. [4].

The objectives of the project MIMAR (MAC/4.6d/066), funded by the European Union included the monitoring, control and mitigation of the observed

changes in the marine ecosystems from Macaronesia. Within the framework of this project, different islands have been sampled within the Cape Verde Archipelago and since 2017 an exhaustive inventory of microalgae species with particular interest on potentially harmful species is being carried out. Sampling has been performed in 32 coastal sites on five Islands: São Vicente, Sal, Maio, Santiago and Boa Vista (Fig.1). Sampling sites included a variety of intertidal and subtidal marine habitats ranging from 1 to 40 meters depth. Habitats included sandy and rocky substrates, macroalgal beds and coral beds (Fig. 2). Benthic microalgae species, both from macroalgae and from artificial substrates were sampled by snorkelling and by SCUBA diving. Water temperature during the sampling period ranged from 24 to 27 °C. Cells were examined with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JEOL JSM-6380 LV) and with light microscopy/fluorescence microscopy (LEICA DM6000 B). Cells were stained with fluorescent stain calcofluor for the examination of their plate tabulation. A total of 140 microalgae species were identified. Diatoms were the most numerous group with 108 species. *Gambierdiscus excentricus* Fraga, *Ostreopsis lenticularis* Y. Fukuyo and *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata* Y. Fukuyo were identified amongst the dinoflagellates.

Gambierdiscus excentricus had an anteroposteriorly compressed lenticular shape. Measurement ranges

Fig. 2. Macroalgae and corals habitat at Baia das Gatas, São Vicente.

Fig. 3. *Gambierdiscus excentricus*. Scanning electron micrographs, apical and ventral views

Fig. 4. *Ostreopsis lenticularis*. Scanning electron micrographs, apical and ventral views

were: depth (D) 84-110 µm, width (W) 70-105 µm, and length 35-40 µm. The thecal plate formula was: Po 4' 6'' 6c ?s 5'' 1p 2'''. Thecal plates were smooth with fine round to oval pores. Apical pore plate Po was oval with a fishhook-shaped slit and was ventrally displaced. First apical plate, 1', was very small. Ratio between plates 2'/3' and 2'/4' suture lengths ranged from 2 to -2.5. Plates 1' and 6'' were very small and facing the posterior part of the cell due to the torsion of the flagellar area which formed a hollow. From this hollow, two flagella emerged, the longitudinal one being perpendicularly projected. The Sp was in the hypotheca, out of the sulcus. The 2'''' plate was about twice as long as wide (Fig. 3).

Ostreopsis lenticularis Y. Fukuyo cells were broadly oval in apical and antapical views, lenticular-shaped, biconvex, and flattened, with the cingu-

lum straight in lateral view. Measurements ranges were: depth (D) 60-105 µm, width (W) 53-74 µm and the DV/W ratio 1.13-1.42 (mean 1.27). The thecal plate formula was: Po 4' 6'' 6c 4?s 5'' 2'''. The apical pore plate Po was long and narrow, slightly curved with the outline of the cell. The fourth apical plate (4')

was elongated and hexagonal, located

Fig. 5. *Ostreopsis lenticularis*. Epifluorescence micrograph showing detail of the thecal surface with two kinds of thecal pores.

mostly on the left side of the cell. The second apical plate (2') was narrow and elongated, and located below the APC, extending dorsally to the Po plate, and reaching about the mid-position of the 3' plate. Plates 5'' were pentagonal and reached half of the DW axis (Fig. 4). The thecal surface was smooth and plates presented numerous pores of two types (Fig. 5). Large pores and small pores visible with the light microscope with epifluorescence and with SEM. Analyses of the LSU rDNA D1-D3 corroborated previous identifications of *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis* species. The analyses of samples from 32 sampling sites showed that *O. lenticularis* was widely distributed in Sal, Sao Vicente and Boa Vista but was not observed in Maio and Santiago. *Ostreopsis lenticularis* cell densities ranged from 50 per sample to 1×10^6 cells per 100 cm^{-2} . *G. excentricus* was distributed in all the islands visited except for Maio. *Gambierdiscus excentricus* concentrations ranged from a few cells per sample to 150 cells per 100 cm^{-2} .

Potentially toxic species of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis* are reported for the first time in the Cape Verde Islands. The presence of these species would explain the ciguatera cases that have been previously documented for this archipelago.

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References

1. Wells M. et al 2015. *Harmful Algae* 14:68-93
2. Hallegraeff GM 2010. *J Phycol* 46: 220-235
3. Silva ES 1956. *Bull LI. F. A. N. XVIII, série A. T. XVIII, sér. A, n°, 2, pp. 335-371*
4. Fraga S et al 2014. *Protist* 165: 839-853.

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Microcystis bloom in Saladito river, central-southern Cuba

Fig. 1. Map showing the cyanobacterial bloom area in Saladito River, central-southern Cuba.

“Water blooms” or simply “blooms” in freshwater reservoirs are mass accumulations of planktonic microalgae or cyanobacteria. Water blooms (“Wasserblüte”) were defined as floating agglomerations in the water surface composed mostly by some blue-green algae (cyanobacteria) [1]. In freshwater systems, these blooms are planktonic communities in which cyanobacteria are dominant. Other microalgal group species, such as the green alga *Botryococcus braunii* Kützing (Trebouxiophyceae) [2], may co-occur with the cyanobacteria, but always as a lesser part of the community. The occurrence of toxic cyanobacterial blooms poses a threat to human health and environmental quality [3, 4].

The unicellular genus *Microcystis*, a producer of microcystins, is one of the most important bloom-forming cyanobacterial genera worldwide, particularly in stagnant freshwater bodies with increasing eutrophication [4]. Komárek [5], reported *Microcystis*, represented by 6 species, as the most frequent bloom-forming genus in stagnant freshwater reservoirs in Cuba, but the central part of the country was not included in his studies. Comas et al. [6] reported blooms from reservoirs in the Cienfuegos province were mainly formed by *M. panniformis* Komárek et

al. and *M. cf. smithii* Komárek et Anagnostidis. Blooms composed by cyanobacterial filamentous genera were also recorded from the same area [7].

The microalgal and cyanobacterial flora of Cuban lotic systems (rivers) is practically unknown and cyanobacterial blooms have not been reported in these systems. During the routine monitoring program for validation of SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) model, a dense cyanobacterial bloom was observed (on June 14th, 2019), in the lower part of the Saladito river (22°16' 43" N; 80° 22' 53" W), Cienfuegos province, Central-southern Cuba. The Saladito River is 17.2 km long with an average depth of 1.24 m. Its waters are used for irrigation and aquaculture [8]. The river flows into the Salado river, which in turn flows into Cienfuegos bay, one of the most important natural resources of the region (Fig. 1). Green water discoloration extended for about 1 km (Fig. 2). The June 2019 bloom was formed by a

Microcystis species with a cell density of 6×10^4 cells mL⁻¹. Low densities of pennate diatoms were also present as accompanying species. No deleterious effects of the bloom on freshwater fauna were observed, but it represented a potential risk to agriculture and aquaculture in the area. Environmental factors favorable for the occurrence of this bloom included high irradiance and water temperature (32.4 °C) during summer. Salinity was 0.26, total solids in suspension 50 mg L⁻¹, dissolved oxygen 17.30 mg L⁻¹ and pH 8.53. The bloom may have also been favored by droughts at the beginning of the rainy period (May-October). These droughts lead to increased stability of the water column and nutrient concentrations.

Taxonomic classification of chroococcalean cyanobacteria is difficult. The genus *Microcystis* is not an exception. Species identification has been based on a few morphological features (shape of colonies, structure of mucilaginous

Fig. 2. *Microcystis* bloom in the Saladito River. A. Bloom and some dried riverine vegetation. B-D. Intense green water discolorations.

Fig. 3. *Microcystis* sp. A-C. Colonies. D. Details of cells inside a colony (Scale bar = 10 µm).

envelope, cell size, presence of aerotopes, etc). These characteristics show a great variability and often the features of several populations overlap the limited morphospecies criteria. In addition, some populations often present local variability. The genus *Microcystis* has a clear genotype delimitation, but many of its intrageneric units are not yet strongly supported [9]. Several *Microcystis* morphospecies, with similar morphology and ecology and classified as the traditional species, occur in different regions of the world. Their accurate identification is useful and necessary for applied hydrobiology and ecological investigations.

Cuban specimens belong to these populations whose characteristics overlap the limited morphospecies criteria. Colonies are spherical, spheroidal to irregularly elongated, flat or twisted, sometimes more or less hollow, with densely agglomerated cells, mostly without holes or seldom with small holes; solitary or after fragmentation of a colony, 2-4 new colonies are formed, remaining into a single mucilaginous envelope. Mucilage is colourless, slimy, with margins diffused, relatively wide, sometimes overlapping cells. Cells are spherical, 3-6 µm in diameter, pale blue-green, with aerotopes. Solitary cells in colony were not observed (Fig. 3).

According to the morphology of the solitary colonies (spheroidal, without holes, 5.6 µm in diameter) the Cuban specimen in this study resembles those of *M. flos-aquae* (Wittrock) Kirchner ex Forti, but composed colonies are not present. The typical *M. flos-aquae* occurs in temperate zones, and is not very common here. Tropical populations under this name are considered problematic [9]. The pantropical *M. panniformis* Komárek et al. forms similar solitary colonies in young stages, composed colonies are not formed and the mucilage margins of colonies are not overlapping the cells, which are smaller (2.5-5 µm in diameter). *M. aeruginosa* f. *flos-aquae* (Wittrock) Elenkin (*M. flos-aquae*) was frequently found as the dominant species in Cuban cyanobacterial blooms [5]; however these populations belong to *M. panniformis* [10]. By the form and structure of the colonies, our specimens could be related also to *M. novacekii* (Komárek) Compere. This tropical species, very rare in warmer areas of temperate zones, forms spherical solitary colonies during its early stages; typical composed colonies are formed in older stages. The mucilage is wide, with delimited margins, rarely diffuse, homogeneous or slightly concentrically lamellated. Cells are spherical, 2.4-6 µm in diameter, densely concentrated in

the center of the colony; a few solitary cells may appear in the mucilage. In our populations the typical solitary cells in mucilage were not observed, neither the concentrically lamellated margins. It is possible that the Cuban specimens could be identified as *M. panniformis* or *M. novacekii*, but further studies about the whole life cycle will be necessary for a reliable identification of this morphotype.

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References

1. Lenz F 1928. Verlag J. Springer, Berlin
2. Fott B 1971. Jena, Germany, 581 pp
3. Carmichael WW 1992. *Appl. Bacteriology* 72: 445-479
4. Carmichael WW & Falconer IR 1993. Academic Press, New York, pp 187-209
5. Komárek J 1984. *Acta Botanica Cubana* 19: 1-33
6. Comas A et al 2010. *HAN* 43: 18-19
7. Comas A & A Moreira 2013. *HAN* 47: 16-17
8. Hernández-Rey A et al 2016. *Editorial Universo Sur*, 161 pp
9. Komárek J & J Komárková 2002. *Czechs Phycology, Olomouc*, 2: 1-24
10. Komárek J et al 2002. *Cryptogamie Algal.* 23(2): 159-177

Authors

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Citizen Science Oceanography in the Strait of Georgia, Canada – an overview of five years of operations

The Citizen Science Oceanography Program for the coastal waters of British Columbia (BC), Canada was proposed by Dr. Eddy Carmack, Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO). Carmack envisioned a ‘mosquito fleet’ of private boats collecting oceanographic data simultaneously throughout the Strait of Georgia (SoG). He said “[using] this citizen science approach, you can get into the shallow waters, you can get up the bays and estuaries. You can get around rocks. You get that quasi-three-dimensional perspective, almost four-dimensional”. Such a program was funded in 2015 by the Pacific Salmon Foundation (PSF) and supported by the Oceans and

Networks Canada (ONC) and DFO.

Keen volunteers from local communities were trained and their boats equipped with the necessary equipment (Fig. 1), and they have made oceanographic measurements and collected samples at ~80 defined locations on the same day approximately every two weeks between February and October, 2015-2019 resulting in complete coverage of the SoG. Oceanographic conditions were measured with CTDs (conductivity, temperature, depth) and water samples were taken for nutrient, phytoplankton, and zooplankton analysis. Samples were analyzed by skilled technicians at DFO, University of Victo-

ria, and PSF. The data collected allows the examination of spatial and temporal variations in the physical and chemical oceanography, and plankton ecology throughout the entire Strait. This information has provided a unique high-resolution data series of the physical and lower trophic state of the SoG: this resolution is crucial for coastal waters as significant changes happen on a fine temporal scale in these areas, and only high frequency sampling can capture it.

Harmful algae monitoring is part of the Citizen Science Program. Some algae cause visible, high cell concentration blooms (that can be harmful or non-harmful) while some algae can cause

Fig. 2. Blooms of *Noctiluca scintillans* in: Salt Spring Island (top), May 2, 2018 (photo by Michael Bahrey); Nelson Island (bottom left), July 25, 2019 (photo by Ted Woodard) and mixed with an *Heterosigma akashiwo* bloom, Kuper Island (bottom right), May 22, 2018 (photo by Michael Bahrey)

Fig. 1. Citizen Scientists sampling in the Strait of Georgia.

harm (e.g. fish kills, shellfish poisoning) at very low concentrations. In the latter case, they are still called blooms because of their effects. These types of blooms can be invisible to the naked eye and only *in-situ* sampling can detect them. During five years of observations, the heaviest blooms were bright orange-red blooms of *Noctiluca scintillans* in 2018 and 2019 (Fig. 2) and the bright turquoise blooms of coccolithophorids in 2016 (Fig. 3). These blooms were visually striking and attracted a lot of public attention and news coverage. Other blooms, visually less prominent but potentially highly significant to marine life included blooms of: *Heterosigma akashiwo*, *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. (Fig. 4), *Gonyaulax* spp., *Rhizosolenia setigera*, and *Dictyocha* spp. Phytoplankton time series obtained through the Citizen Science Oceanography Pro-

gram showed clear seasonal and spatial patterns of some species. Investigation of the relationship between environmental factors and blooms will improve our understanding of regional bloom dynamics.

Citizen scientists sample areas close to where they live and to which they have emotional connections. Giving them the ability to measure their own waters is empowering. Carmack says that “if you look at bang for buck, value for money and engagement of people, and drawing kids into the game, it should be on every coast in the world”. ONC states that “historically, oceanographic data collection relied on specialty research vessels and highly trained scientists in limited locations. These new tools reduce the high cost of sporadic data collection, increasing the geographic range of quality measurements.” Spencer Taft,

Tsleil-Waututh Nation adds that Citizen Science monitoring of the SoG “will allow us to precisely track changes as the waters are affected by climate change, development and restoration activities”. October 2019 marks the end of the fifth year that the Citizen Science Oceanography Program has been carried out in the SoG: PSF hopes to raise funds to continue this program in 2020.

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Fig. 3. Bloom of Coccolithophorids, Maple Bay, 2016 (photo by Will Duguid)

Fig. 4. Citizen Science samples: left, *Noctiluca scintillans*; middle, *Heterosigma akashiwo*; right, *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp.

Multicoloured algal blooms in the NW Adriatic during 2018

The northern Adriatic is characterized by shallow waters (mean depth about 35 m), a weak bathymetric gradient along the main axis and a high riverine input on the western side, affecting both the circulation regime and the trophic status. As a consequence, the productivity of the western coastal waters of the North Adriatic is markedly higher compared to the general oligotrophic conditions of the Mediterranean Sea. The spatial distribution and the seasonal variability of phytoplankton communities in the Adriatic Sea are mainly driven by major river discharge (and therefore by the rainfall regime), in combination with the stratification/

mixing condition [1].

Since the last decade, the irregularity of meteorological events has markedly altered the seasonal cycle of phytoplankton. During rainy years, the very intense and sudden rainfall has caused anomalous blooms throughout the year [2]. This was observed during 2018, when several intense anomalous blooms occurred along the Marche coast (northern Adriatic Sea) associated with water discoloration. Here we have summarized the major events that occurred.

In April an exceptional bloom of the diatom *Chaetoceros socialis* (Fig 1) reaching cell densities of 10^7 cells

l^{-1} caused an intense brown water discoloration along the Ancona coasts. Blooms of that species are not common, although they have been reported in the past. No cases of anoxia or mortality of benthic organisms were reported.

In May, an unusual green coloration extended for several kilometres offshore, causing concern among bathers and yachtsmen. Microscopy analysis revealed that the causative organism of this bloom was the dictyochophyte *Vicicitus globosus* (formerly *Chattonella globosa*, raphidophytes, Fig 2). The presence of *V. globosus* in this area was reported only once in 2012 [3], and although this species is indicated as potential fish killer, fish mortalities were not observed.

In July in the coastal waters north of Ancona, an intense bloom of the raphidophyte *Fibrocapsa japonica* was observed (Fig 3), causing a brick-red discoloration. The first report of a *F. japonica* bloom in the Adriatic Sea dates back to 1997 in the Marche coast [4] and a bloom generically ascribed to raphidophyceans was reported in the southern part of Emilia Romagna coast even in 1994 [5]. *F. japonica* blooms reach cell densities of 10^7 cells l^{-1} and have occurred almost each year in July – August, both in Marche and Emilia Romagna coasts, typically extending from the shoreline to 300 m offshore and showing an intensification of colour in the early afternoon. Except for a detriment to tourism and recreational activities due to the intense water discoloration, fish kills have been observed only once in front of the Ancona port, but autopsies revealed that the cause of death was not due to haemolytic toxins, but to asphyxia [6].

In August, a greenish-brown water discoloration was observed due to an intense proliferation of an unidentified gymnodinioid (Fig. 4), and in November an impressive green tide due to a mixed diatom community and *Prorocentrum cordatum* (Fig. 5) extended from the shoreline to several kilometres offshore.

Such events have been related to the intense and irregular rainfalls that occurred during 2018, causing sudden massive releases of nutrient-rich

Fig. 1. *Chaetoceros socialis* intricate colonies.

Fig. 2 Greenish waters due to *Vicicitus globosus* bloom.

Fig. 3. Brick-red water discoloration from a *Fibrocapsa japonica* bloom.

Fig. 4. A bloom of an unidentified gymnodinioid caused a brown-greenish discoloration.

Fig. 6. *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* bloom causing bleaching of macroalgal thalli.

Fig. 5. Green colored waters from a mixed bloom of diatoms and *Prorocentrum cordatum*.

Fig. 7. Field sample showing *Takayama tasmanica* and diatoms.

freshwater that enhance phytoplankton blooms.

Benthic substrata hosted summer-autumn blooms of the toxic benthic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*. This species has regularly occurred along the rocky coast of the Conero Riviera since 2006, reaching abundances among the highest in the entire Mediterranean Sea (order of magnitude of 10^4 cells cm^{-2} , 10^6 cells g^{-1} fw) [7]. In 2018, an *Ostreopsis* bloom started at the beginning of August, reaching the maximum values at mid-September (Fig. 6). No evident noxious effects on human health were observed but impacts on benthic organisms were detected.

Finally, in December, a gymnodinioid considered toxic to marine fauna i.e. *Takayama tasmanica*, identified through microscopy and molecular analyses (Fig. 7), was reported for the first time in the area, although in non-blooming cell concentrations.

References

1. Degobbi D et al 2000. *Int J Environ Pollut* 13: 495–533
2. Totti C et al 2019. *J Mar Sys* 193: 137–153
3. ARPAM 2012. *Relazione annuale sulla qualità delle acque di balneazione*. <http://www.arpa.marche.it/index.php/pubblicazioni-arpa-marche>

4. Cucchiari E et al 2007. *Harmful Algae* 7: 405–414
5. Regione Emilia-Romagna 1994. *Eutrofizzazione delle Acque costiere dell'Emilia-Romagna. Rapporto annuale 1994*, 227 pp (in Italian)
6. Mattei et al (eds) 2005. *Rapporto ISTISAN 05/29*, 227 pp. (in Italian)
7. Accoroni et al 2012. *Cryptogamie Algol* 33(2): 191–198

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A bloom of *Prorocentrum triestinum* in the Hossegor Marine Lake (France)

Phytoplankton communities in the Hossegor marine lake (Southern French Atlantic coast, Fig. 1) have been monthly monitored since 1997 to protect human health (REPHY network: monitoring of toxin producing species which may contaminate cultivated oysters) and environmental (EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) network) purposes.

This shallow, eutrophic marine lake which is subject to opportunistic green algae blooms is fed by a narrow canal that receives water from the ocean and

two small rivers. Water temperature ranges between 10 and 25° C and salinity between 20 and 35. In this lake, the phytoplanktonic communities are usually dominated by marine species (*i.e.* *Leptocylindrus minimus*, *Dactyliosolen fragilissimus*, *Cylindrotheca closterium*) whilst blooms of freshwater species (Cyanobacteria: *Planktothrix agardhii*) may occur during periods of high river discharge.

In August 2019, following the observation of a brown coloured water

phenomenon, analysis of water samples revealed high abundances (about 6 million cells per liter) of *Prorocentrum triestinum* (class *Dinophyceae*, order *Prorocentrales*, Fig. 2). This was the first observation of this species in this lake. Since then, its presence has been quite sporadic due to the high tidal-induced renewal of water within the lake.

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Fig. 1. Study area - Hossegor marine lake

Fig. 2. *Prorocentrum triestinum* (fixed with neutral Lugol's solution) in a lake water sample collected during August 2019.

Continued from page 7

Fig. 3. Micrographs of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*

Mediterranean Sea. Results of this study may contribute to a better understanding of *Ostreopsis* ecology and population dynamics and its trends in Alexandria waters. In addition, it provides the basis for an effective bloom management and mitigation of its effects.

References

- Mikhail S 2007. *Chem Ecol* 23(5): 393-407
- Imai I & M Yamaguchi 2012. *Harmful Algae* 14: 46-70
- Klöpper S et al 2013. *Eur J Phycol* 48:79-92
- Imai I et al 2006. *Jap Plank Benth Res* 1:71-84
- Haque SH & Y Onoue 2002. *Environ Toxicol* 17: 113-118
- Hallegraeff GM & Y Hara 2003. *UNES Pub, Paris*, 511-522
- Mikhail S & W Labib 2012. In: Kim HG et al (eds), *Harmful Algae 2012, ISSHA 2014*, pp 41-44 (on line)
- Hosny SH 2016. PhD Thesis, Faculty of Science, Tanta University, Egypt
- Parsons ML et al 2012. *Harmful Algae* 14: 107-129
- Ciminiello P et al 2011. *Toxicon* 57: 362-36
- Tubaro A et al 2011. *Toxicon* 57: 478-495
- Mikhail SK & W Labib 2014. Abstracts. *Estuaries & Coastal Protected Areas, Izmir, Turkey*, 4-6 Novembre 2014
- Hosny SH & W Labib 2019. *J Oceanogr Mar Res* 7:1
- Boisnoir A et al 2019. *Harmful Algae* 81: 18-29
- Yamaguchi H et al 2012. *Fish Sci* 78: 993-1000

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The International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) annual science conference took place in Gothenburg, Sweden, 9-12th Sept 2019 with 738 participants from 38 countries attending. The conference opened with a lively panel discussion around sustainable management of the sea particularly in relation to the UN sustainable development goals. Daily keynote presentations included 'The future of fish and its role in securing food for a 9-billion world' by Manual Barange, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 'Climate-driven redistribution of ocean life and its implications for society' by Greta Pecl from the Centre for Marine Socioecology (CMS), Australia and 'Re-examining physical-biological linkages in a changing ocean: what will we need to know by 2030?' by Cisco Werner, NOAA Fisheries, USA. These presentations can be viewed online at <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL4gXA2v1PWKOWlHZKXe7ClpaVmAX4lnuM>.

Eighteen science theme sessions addressed a variety of topics including oceanography, fisheries, aquaculture and man's interaction with the ocean. Theme session J focused on 'HABs and Jellyfish- Impacts on ecosystems and ecosystems services'. The session was convened by Eileen Bresnan (ICES-IOC WG Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics), Sophie Pitois (ICES WG Zooplankton Ecology) and Mike Rust (ICES Aquaculture steering group) as a first step to begin a dialogue between the three different work strands within ICES. HAB presentations focussed on reviews of HAB monitoring and impact data collected over the last two decades with presentations from the North Atlantic Area, Irish coastal waters, and the Kattegat-Skagerrak/the Baltic Sea. In contrast to HABs, routine monitoring for jellyfish is not established in many areas. A new method to use fish surveys to collect jellyfish data was presented and molecular methods which showed them to be a component of the diet of

forage fish in the Celtic Seas and Western Channel. Modelling methods were used by both HAB and jellyfish scientists to look at bloom advection and development with a view to providing a service for the aquaculture industry. Challenges for offshore aquaculture, the distribution of benthic dinoflagellates in Sweden, impacts from filamentous algae on herring larvae in the Baltic were the focus of poster presentations. Conveners welcome new members to the working groups and can be contacted via the email addresses below.

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In Memoriam – Professor Tufan Koray

It is with a heavy heart we announce that Professor Tufan Koray, internationally recognized phytoplankton taxonomist and ecologist, died on March 9, 2019, after a short illness, in Hamburg, Germany.

Dr. Koray was an exceptionally kind and thoughtful person, known for his love of nature, art, music, and animals. He was able to build a distinguished career focused on the taxonomy and ecology of plankton, especially toxic/harmful microalgae species, as well as pollution in marine ecosystems and fish farms. Overcoming several setbacks, he became the pioneer and founder of modern phytoplankton taxonomy in his country, making a significant contribution to the scientific knowledge in this region.

Dr. Koray was born 1954 in Turkey, received his PhD in 1985 from Ege University, Izmir, Turkey, and was a faculty member at the same university until

2016. After his retirement, he moved to Hamburg, Germany, where he spent his last years pursuing his passion of art and music.

As well as being a very thorough and knowledgeable reviewer of the scientific literature, Dr. Koray was the editor, associate editor/board member for several journals in Turkey, such as *Ege Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* and *Turkish Journal of Botany*. He and his team also published *The Micro-*

planktonic Atlas of the Turkish Seas in 2007. He was a member of ASLO, and a contributor to ERMS, FAO/UNEP-MAP, SCIENCEnet, IOC-UNESCO Harmful Algal Bloom Programme, and the International Scientific Community Expertise Center for Taxonomic Identification.

Dr. Koray was an outstanding scientist and committed teacher and mentor, and he has certainly left his mark on our world. The scientific community will miss him.

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11th Irish Shellfish Safety Workshop

At the 11th Shellfish Safety Workshop held in the Radisson Blu Hotel Athlone, Ireland, Joe Silke, Director of Marine Environment and Food Safety Services at the Marine Institute said, “Ireland’s Shellfish Safety Monitoring Programme ensures that shellfish placed on the market meet the highest standards of food safety. This workshop enables scientists and regulators to exchange information and discuss the latest research, advances in technology, and forecast any issues for the industry, to help ensure Ireland continues to offer high-quality products.”

More than 90 shellfish producers and processors, scientists, researchers, agencies and stakeholder representatives recently attended the Shellfish Safety Workshop to discuss the latest advances in shellfish safety in Ireland.

The workshop, held on 8th October, was hosted by the Marine Institute and co-sponsors Food Safety Authority of Ireland, Sea Fisheries Protection Authority and Bord Iascaigh Mhara. The event offered an opportunity to exchange information on the latest re-

search and information on the cause and control of shellfish products harvested and farmed around Ireland’s coast.

Speakers included Dr Conor Graham, GMIT Marine and Freshwater Research Centre on the development of the world’s first scientific-based shellfish traceability tool. This unique tool used trace elemental fingerprinting of shellfish soft tissues and shells to identify the harvest location of blue mussels and scallops with 100% success, including mussels reared from two sites located just 6km apart within the one bay.

Other speakers included Dr Monika Dhanji Rapkova, Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science on the learnings on regulated and emerging biotoxins in British shellfish. Dr Eileen Bresnan, Marine Scotland Science presented a talk on the regional distribution of harmful algal events in North Atlantic Area. Dave Clarke, Marine Institute also talked about the insights and perspectives on monitoring algal and biotoxin events in Irish coastal waters from the past 20 years.

Micheál O’Mahony of the Sea Fisheries Protection Authority presented on the recently published European baseline survey of norovirus in oysters, while Dr Sinéad Keaveney, Marine Institute discussed the survey in the Irish context.

There were also a series of flash presentations from representatives of the Marine Institute, Bord Iascaigh Mhara, Sea Fisheries Protection Authority, Food Safety Authority of Ireland, Dublin City University, Sligo Institute of Technology and Health Services Executive.

The proceedings of the workshop are currently being compiled for publication in the coming weeks and will be available for download from the Marine Institute’s Open Access Repository.

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Fig. 1. Participants at the 11th Irish Shellfish Safety Workshop

Fig. 2. Oyster Farm. Photo courtesy of Fionn O'Fearthail, Marine Institute

Marine Institute

The Marine Institute is the state agency responsible for marine research, technology development and innovation in Ireland. The Marine Institute provides government, public agencies and the maritime industry with a range of scientific, advisory and economic development services that inform policy-making, regulation and the sustainable management and growth of Ireland's marine resources.

Foras na Mara
Marine Institute

Fig. 3. Micheál O'Mahony of the Sea Fisheries Protection Authority

The 33rd annual meeting of the Australasian Society for Phycology and Aquatic Botany (ASPAB)

The 33rd annual ASPAB meeting was held at NIWA's Greta Point site in Wellington, New Zealand on 11-13 November 2019. This year most presentations were on macroalgae although in the past microalgae and HABS have been a hot topic. This year's HAB presentations were by Rossella Nicolai (MSc student, Victoria University of Wellington, Cawthron Institute), who presented 'Investigating the active export of microcystins in freshwater cyanobacteria', and Dr Tomohiro Nishimura (JSPS Overseas Research Fellow, Cawthron Institute), who spoke on the 'Diversity, diarrhetic shellfish toxin production, and distribution of benthic dinoflagellates *Prorocentrum lima* complex and *P. caipirignum* in Japan' (Nishimura et al. 2019). The meeting draws together algal research-

ers from across Australia and New Zealand and is a great opportunity for students to present their work.

ASPAB was established in 1980 and its aims are to promote, develop and assist the study of, or an interest in, phycology (the study of macro- and micro-algae such as seaweeds and phytoplankton) and aquatic botany (the study of aquatic plants) within Australasia and elsewhere (see <https://www.aspab.org/>).

The next meeting, the 34th annual ASPAB meeting, will be held in Australia in 2020. The date and venue will be announced on the website. Marine and freshwater algae and aquatic plants researchers and students from within Australasia and from overseas are welcome to attend.

References

1. Nishimura T, Uchida H, Noguchi R, et al. 2019. Harmful Algae (on-line). doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101687

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Participants at the 33rd ASPAB meeting, Wellington, New Zealand

Forthcoming events

Call for abstracts - ICHA 2020

The Organizing Committee is pleased to announce the call for abstracts and pre-registration for the 19th International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms to be held from the 11th to the 16th of October 2020 in La Paz, Baja California Sur, Mexico. La Paz is a small, secure and vibrant maritime city where many scientific institutions are situated – an ideal city for the meeting!

The organizing committee invites the submission of abstracts within a broad range of topics related to the study of harmful algae from basic studies to future ap-

plications. For the full list of topics, please visit the conference website (icha2020.com/Secciones/contenido/33). The deadline for submitting an abstract for a poster, speed-talk or oral presentation is the 12th of April 2020. All abstracts must be submitted at the conference website (icha2020.com/Secciones/contenido/35).

Participants wishing to receive the ISSHA member rate for the conference registration must join ISSHA or renew their memberships prior to 12th of June 2020.

A visa may be required for participants from some countries. Please check visa regulations well in advance with your local Mexican Embassy or Consulate for official instructions on the specific visa regulations and application procedures.

As the main host of the conference, ISSHA will support student travel awards, achievement awards, and the popular ISSHA auction!

Modeling and Prediction of Harmful Algal Blooms: Emerging Methods, Regional Problem-solving, and Patterns of Global Change

IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB and EuroMarine are pleased to announce this international workshop to be held in Glasgow, Scotland, 18-21 May 2020.

The typical HAB is a regional- or local-scale phenomenon, a “perfect storm” of environmental conditions, ocean transport and mixing patterns, and microbial ecology. Because of this complexity, prediction of HABs is a grand challenge that requires multidisciplinary dialogue among physical scientists, biologists, computer modellers, and technologists, as well as community stakeholders and the government and industry end-users of prediction systems.

This 3.5-day workshop will combine oral and poster presentations, round-table discussions, and tutorials in order to:

- Increase awareness of the range of modelling and observational tools that are in our community toolbox (or should be);
- Help the HAB community speak with one voice regarding climate-change impacts on the global ocean; and
- Help scientists and technologists develop creative approaches to meeting the needs of coastal communities, governments, and industry worldwide.

Hands-on tutorials will include “Getting started with...” sessions on remote-sensing data, machine-learning approaches, global climate model output, and dynamical plankton models, with presenters including Clarissa Anderson, (SCCOOS/

Scripps, USA), Raphael Kudela (UC Santa Cruz, USA), Charles Stock (NOAA GFDL, USA), and Androniki Tamvakis (University of the Aegean, Greece).

Abstract submission is open through **15 Dec 2019** at hab-modelworkshop.sccoos.org, for presentations and facilitated discussions in the areas of:

1. Regional problem-solving: linking models, observations, and stakeholder needs
2. Emerging approaches and technologies: physical and ecological model methods and observational capacities that open up new directions in HAB prediction
3. Global patterns and global change: links between HABs and environmental drivers at large spatial scales and on long time horizons
4. Scalable solutions: applications of global models, remote sensing, and other communal resources to predicting HABs and managing their impacts in data- and resource-poor systems

We particularly invite scientists outside North America and Europe, and early-career scientists in general, to propose discussion topics and get involved in facilitating the meeting. **Funding is available to cover travel costs** for a subset of participants, with the goal of increasing international and career-stage diversity as much as possible.

Las Palmas
de Gran Canaria
July, 13th - 17th 2020

12th International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates

The Canarian HABs Observatory (OCH) hosts the 12th edition of the International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates (DINO12), to be held from 13th to 17th July 2020 at the Alfredo Kraus Auditorium in Las Canteras beach, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain. The International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates (DINO) has been held on a con-

tinuous basis at different places of the world since 1978.

DINO12 will have global warming as an overarching theme in the context of dinoflagellates and their cysts. As usual, the conference will gather biologists working with modern dinoflagellates and geologists working with fossil dinoflagellates.

For further information visit: www.dino12conference.com

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 64:
March 1st 2020

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Lay-out

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